
Investigation of Corrosion Inhibition of Zn metal in 0.1M HNO₃ by Terminalia Catappa

Alhaji M. Kolo^{1*}, Ali Yakubu², Audu A. Jibrin³, Ali Ibrahim⁴

¹Department of Chemistry, Corrosion Protection and Material Science Laboratory, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria

²Department of Chemistry, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Bauchi State, Nigeria

³Department of Chemistry, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Bauchi State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Chemistry, Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel, Jigawa State, Nigeria

Abstract Corrosion inhibition potential of *Terminalia catappa* (TC) leaves for zinc in HNO₃ medium was studied using weight loss, Fourier Transform Infra-Red (FTIR) and scanning electron microscopy. The corrosion inhibition mechanism of the plant extract on the zinc surface in 0.1 M HNO₃ acid at different temperatures (303 – 333K) show that the inhibition efficiency (IE) increases with increase in concentration of the inhibitor but decreases with increase in temperature throughout the test period, indicating a physisorption of extract on the zinc surface. The inhibited and uninhibited corrosion reaction of zinc in HNO₃ medium was found to be spontaneous, first order, exothermic and occurred with increasing degree of order. The adsorption characteristic of the inhibitor was best described by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. Scanning electron microscopy results indicated that the inhibitor formed a protective cover on the surface of the metal and thereby inhibited its corrosion. While the results from the FTIR study showed that some functional groups of the inhibitor may have been used in the formation of bonds and adsorption layer between Zn and the inhibitor which indicates that there is interaction between the inhibitor and the studied metal.

Keywords *Terminalia catappa*, Zinc, Corrosion inhibition, Adsorption

1. Introduction

Corrosion is the deterioration of materials by chemical interaction with their environment [1]. The consequences of corrosion are many and varied and the effects of these on the safe, reliable and efficient operation of equipment or structures are often more serious than simple loss of a mass of a metal. Due to problems from corrosion that are confronting industries; several methods of corrosion control and prevention have been put in place. These include: cathodic protection, lubrication, anodic protection, alloying, coating, inhibition etc. The choice and application of any of the methods is based on their efficiency, economic factors and the nature of the corrosive environment [2].

The use of inhibitors is one of the most practical methods for protection against corrosion in corrosive environments. Inhibitors are chemicals that directly or indirectly coat a film on a metal surface to protect it from its environment [3]. Most of the known corrosion inhibitors are synthetic chemicals, expensive and very hazardous to environment. [4].

The use of natural products otherwise tagged —green corrosion inhibitors| has been advocated because of the cost, toxic nature and environmentally unfriendliness of some of the inorganic and organic corrosion inhibitors. More so,

they are readily available, cheap and a renewable source of materials. A lot of natural products were previously used as corrosion inhibitors for different metals in various environments and their optimum concentrations were reported [1, 5-12]. Very encouraging results have been obtained in this regard. An attempt at making a contribution to this growing research area has necessitated the present investigation,

Therefore the objective of the present study is to investigate the inhibitive and adsorption properties of ethanol extracts of *Terminalia catappa* (TC) leaves for the corrosion of zinc in HNO_3 medium.

The Leaf of TC has been analyzed with some of the following major phytochemicals identified; α -farnesene (21.3%), octadecane (11.7%), hexadecanoic acid (9.5%), dibutyl phthalate (9.1%), 1,2,3-trimethoxy-5-(2-propenyl)- benzene (6.6%), neoisothujol (5.8%), 1,2,4-trimethoxy-5-(1-propenyl)-benzene (4.5%) 6,10,14-trimethyl-2-pentadecanoic, 1-(2,3,6-trimethyl phenyl)-(E)-3-buten-2-one, geranyl acetone, hexadecanoic acid (21.0%) and 2-ethyl-3,6-dimethylpyrazine (19.2%), (Z)-phytol (41.2%), fatty acid palmitic acid (11.0%), and the (E)-nerolidol (4.7%) [13-15]. The presence of these phytochemicals in the compound makes it suitable as a good corrosion inhibitor since they possess π -bond, aromatic system, conjugated bond, heteroatoms and long carbon chains [16].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The sheets of zinc, A72357 type used for this study were obtained from the Novara group Limited England. The composition of the zinc metal in (% wt) as determined by quantitative method of analysis using NEX CG Energy Dispersive X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (ED XRF) is Zn (99.591), Sr (0.227), Fe (0.094), Co (0.011), Ni (0.011), Si (0.021), and Zr (0.045). Each sheet was 0.4 mm in thickness and were mechanically pressed cut into 5 x 4 cm coupons for weight loss and 2 x 3 cm for electrochemical. The coupons were degreased by washing in absolute ethanol, dried in acetone and stored in moisture free desiccators before use [17].

Analar grade reagents were used. These included concentrated Trioxonitrate (V) acid, ethanol and silver nitrate.

2.2. Preparation of samples

Terminalia catappa (TC), is popularly known as ‘fruit’ in South west Nigeria or ‘mbansan mbakara’ in Efik, South-South Nigeria. It was obtained from Gwange Ward, Damaturu, Yobe State (Lat. $11^{\circ}44.820'N$, Long. $011^{\circ}58.153'E$) in North-East Nigeria. The major phytochemicals in TC have been established as alkaloids, resins, steroids, tannins, saponins and phenols. The functional groups of $-NH$ and $-OH$ are present in the identified phytochemicals [18]. The leaves were washed with water, shade dried, grinded and soaked in a solution of ethanol for 48 hours. After 48 hours, the sample was filtered. The filtrate was subjected to evaporation at 338K ($65^{\circ}C$) in order to ensure the sample was free of ethanol.

The concentration of acid (HNO_3) used for the study were 0.1 M while the concentrations of the inhibitor (*Terminalia catappa* leaves) were 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 g (per liter of the acid solution). These were dissolved in 1liter solution containing 0.1 M of HNO_3 respectively.

2.3. Corrosion monitoring

2.3.1 Weight loss method

A previously weighed metal (zinc sheet) was completely immersed in 250 ml of the test solution (different concentrations of acid, inhibitor as described above) in an open beaker. The beaker was inserted into a water bath maintained at a temperature of 303 K. Similar experiments were repeated at 313 K, 323 K and 333 K. In each case, the weight of the sample before immersion was measured using Scaltec high precision balance (Model SPB31). Prior to measurement, each coupon was washed in 5 % chromic acid solution (containing 1% silver nitrate) and rinsed in de-ionised water.

The difference in weight for a period of 168 hours was taken as total weight loss. The inhibition efficiency (% I) for each inhibitor was calculated using equation 1 [19],

$$\%I = \left(1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2}\right) \times 100 \quad 1$$

where W_1 and W_2 are the weight losses (g/dm^3) for zinc in the presence and absence of inhibitor in HNO_3 solution respectively. The degree of surface coverage θ is given by the equation 2:

$$x = \left(1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2}\right) \quad 2$$

The corrosion rates for zinc corrosion in different concentrations of the acid and other media have been determined for 168h immersion period from weight loss using Equation 3.

$$CR = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{At} \quad 3$$

where CR is the corrosion rate of zinc, A is the surface area of the zinc coupon in cm^2 and t is the period of immersion in hours.

2.3.2. FTIR Analysis

FTIR analysis of the *Terminalia catappa* (TC) leaves and those of the corrosion products were carried out using Cary-630 Agilent Fourier Transform Infra-red Spectrophotometer. The analysis was carried out by scanning the sample through a wave number range of 650 to 4000 cm^{-1} .

2.3.3. Scanning electron Microscopy Studies

A scanning electron microscope (SEM) model JSM-5600 LV, was used to analyze the morphology of the zinc surface without and with inhibitor added. The sample was mounted on a metal stub and sputtered with gold in order to make the sample conductive, and the images were taken at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV using different magnifications.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Weight loss study

The variation of weight loss with time for the corrosion of zinc in HNO_3 solutions containing various concentrations of *Terminalia catappa* (TC) leaves are presented in Figures 1 to 4. From the Figures, it can be seen that weight loss of zinc for the blank is higher than those obtained for solutions containing various concentrations of TC leave extract indicating that it inhibited the corrosion of zinc in HNO_3 solutions. Also, the weight loss of zinc decreases with increasing concentration of the TC leaves extract indicating that the leaf extract is an adsorption inhibitor. For an adsorption inhibitor, weight loss is expected to decrease with increase in concentration [1]. It can be deduced from the plots that weight loss of zinc increases with increase in the period of time and with increase in temperature indicating that the rate of corrosion of zinc increases with time and with increase in temperature.

Figure 1: Variation of weight loss with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC as inhibitor at 303 K

Figure 2: Variation of weight loss with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC as inhibitor at 313 K

Figure 3: Variation of weight loss with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC as inhibitor at 323 K

Figure 4: Variation of weight loss with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC as inhibitor at 333 K

Values of the corrosion rates of zinc in the absence and presence of extract of TC, and their corresponding percentage inhibition efficiencies obtained from equation 1 – 3 are recorded in Table 1. From the results obtained, it is evident that the corrosion rate of zinc in the presence of extract of TC have been found to decrease with increase in the concentration of the extract, indicating that the extract retarded the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO₃ and proportionately that the inhibition efficiencies of extract of TC increased with increase in the concentration of the extracts. From the values of the degree of surface coverage obtained, it can be deduced that TC retarded the corrosion of zinc in solution of HNO₃, such that the rate of retardation decreases with increase in concentration but increases with increase in temperature.

Table 1: Corrosion rate (CR) of zinc, inhibition efficiencies (IE) and degree of surface coverage for TC leaves extract in various media

Temperature	Systems	Corrosion rate (gh ⁻¹ cm ²)	I. E (%)	Degree of surface coverage (θ)
303K	Blank (0.1 M HNO ₃) at 303 K	0.000105	-	-
	0.1 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 303 K	0.0000515	71.05	0.7105
	0.2 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 303 K	0.0000505	73.44	0.7344
	0.3 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 303 K	0.0000501	76.18	0.7618
	0.4 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 303 K	0.0000472	80.88	0.8088
	0.5 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 303 K	0.0000460	84.10	0.8410
313K	Blank (0.1 M HNO ₃) at 313 K	0.000211	-	-
	0.1 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 313 K	0.0000651	54.90	0.5490
	0.2 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 313 K	0.0000643	60.32	0.6032
	0.3 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 313 K	0.0000634	63.28	0.6328
	0.4 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 313 K	0.0000625	65.43	0.6543
	0.5 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 313 K	0.0000613	69.22	0.6922
323K	Blank (0.1 M HNO ₃) at 323 K	0.000351	-	-
	0.1 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 323 K	0.0000676	51.39	0.5139
	0.2 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 323 K	0.0000665	53.87	0.5387
	0.3 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 323 K	0.0000656	57.03	0.5703
	0.4 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 323 K	0.0000648	59.90	0.5990
	0.5 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 323 K	0.0000614	63.73	0.6373
333K	Blank (0.1 M HNO ₃) at 333 K	0.000393	-	-
	0.1 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 333 K	0.0000698	49.89	0.4989
	0.2 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 333 K	0.0000689	52.94	0.5294
	0.3 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 333 K	0.0000618	55.57	0.5557
	0.4 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 333 K	0.0000571	57.94	0.5794
	0.5 gl ⁻¹ of TC leaf extract at 333 K	0.0000559	60.15	0.6015

3.2. Kinetic study

The kinetics of corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO₃, solutions was studied at 303, 313, 323 and 333 K by fitting data obtained from weight loss measurements into equation 4.

$$-\log(\text{weight loss}) = \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad 4$$

where k_1 is the first order rate constant and t is the period of contact.

The test revealed that plotting of values of $-\log(\text{weight loss})$ versus time (Figures 5 to 8) yielded straight line indicating that the corrosion reaction of zinc in solutions of HNO₃ is consistent with a first order kinetics [19-20]. Values of rate constants calculated from the slopes of the plots are presented in Table 2. The results obtained indicate that the rate constants decrease with increasing concentration of the respective inhibitor. Also, the rate constants were also found to increase with rise in temperature. The first order rate constant is related to the half-life of the corrosion reaction of zinc according to the following equation,

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k_1}$$

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where $t_{1/2}$ is the half – life of the corrosion reaction of zinc.

Figure 5: Variation of $-\log(\text{weight loss})$ with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC at 333 K

Figure 6: Variation of $-\log(\text{weight loss})$ with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC at 323 K

Figure 7: Variation of $-\log(\text{weight loss})$ with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC at 313 K

Figure 8: Variation of $-\log(\text{weight loss})$ with time for the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 containing various concentrations of TC at 303 K

Table 2: Kinetic parameters for the inhibition of the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 by TC

Temperature	Inhibitor's concentration	Slope	K_1	$t_{1/2}$ (day)
303 K	0.5g/L	0.0180	0.041454	16.71
	0.4 g/L	0.0252	0.058036	11.94
	0.3 g/L	0.0266	0.06126	11.31
	0.2 g/L	0.0279	0.064254	10.79
	0.1 g/L	0.0291	0.067017	10.34
	Blank	0.0309	0.071163	9.74
313 K	0.5g/L	0.0192	0.044218	15.67
	0.4 g/L	0.0285	0.065636	10.59
	0.3 g/L	0.0292	0.067248	10.31
	0.2 g/L	0.0315	0.072545	9.55
	0.1 g/L	0.0329	0.075769	9.15
	Blank	0.0344	0.079223	8.75
323 K	0.5g/L	0.0232	0.05343	12.97
	0.4 g/L	0.0328	0.075538	9.17
	0.3 g/L	0.0339	0.078072	8.88
	0.2 g/L	0.0357	0.082217	8.43
	0.1 g/L	0.0379	0.087284	7.94
	Blank	0.0388	0.089356	7.76
333 K	0.5g/L	0.0258	0.059417	11.66
	0.4 g/L	0.0409	0.094193	7.36
	0.3 g/L	0.0459	0.105708	6.56
	0.2 g/L	0.0469	0.108011	6.42
	0.1 g/L	0.0499	0.11492	6.03
	Blank	0.0529	0.121829	5.69

Using equation 5, values of the half-life for the various concentrations of the inhibitor were calculated and are also presented in Table 2. The results reveal that the half-life of zinc for the blank is lower than those obtained in the presence of the inhibitor indicating that the inhibitor increases the half-life of metal in HNO_3 solutions. Also, the half-lives were found to increase with increasing containing various concentrations of the inhibitor. The action of TC as inhibitor according to Eddy *et al.*, [21] may therefore be due to the type of interaction between the inhibitor and zinc surface.

3.3. Thermodynamic study

In order to calculate the activation energy of the corrosion reaction of zinc in 0.1 M HNO₃, the Arrhenius equation (Equation 6) was used.

$$\ln(CR) = \ln A - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (6)$$

where CR is the corrosion rate of zinc, A is the Arrhenius or pre-exponential factor, R is the universal gas constant and T is the temperature. Equation 6 reveals that a plot of ln(CR) versus 1/T is expected to be linear, with slope and intercept equal to E_a/R and ln A respectively. Through the plot of ln(CR) versus 1/T (Figure 9), values of E_a were found to range from 9.97 to 11.29 J/mol (mean = 10.60J/mol). These values, together with the degree of linearity (R^2) are recorded in Table 3. From the results, it was seen that the degree of linearity of the plot was high confirming that Arrhenius equation is applicable to the inhibited corrosion reaction of zinc in 0.1 M HNO₃. The average value of E_a was found to be higher than the average value obtained for the blank indicating that TC retards the corrosion of zinc in the studied media.

Figure 9: Arrhenius plots for the inhibition of the corrosion of Zinc in 0.1 M HNO₃ by TC

Table 3: Arrhenius parameters for the inhibition of the corrosion of zinc by TC

System	Slope	Intercept	E_a (J/mol)	A	R^2
Blank	0.8215	-5.725	6.829951	0.00326	0.9708
0.1 g/L	1.3582	-4.2205	11.29207	0.01469	0.9865
0.2 g/L	1.3512	-4.304	11.23388	0.01351	0.9908
0.3 g/L	1.2454	-4.7821	10.35426	0.008378	0.9925
0.4 g/L	1.2199	-4.899	10.14225	0.007454	0.97888
0.5 g/L	1.1993	-5.1035	9.97	6.08E-06	0.9600

The transition state equation was used to calculate the thermodynamic parameters (free energy of adsorption, standard entropy change of adsorption and the standard enthalpy of adsorption of the inhibitor) of adsorption of TC on zinc surface. The transition state equation is represented as Equation 7.

$$CR = \frac{RT}{N_h} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S_{ads}^0}{T}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta H_{ads}^0}{RT}\right) \quad 7$$

where CR is the corrosion rate at the temperature, T, R is the universal gas constant, N is the Avogadro's number, h is the Planck constant, ΔS_{ads}^0 is the standard entropy change of adsorption and ΔH_{ads}^0 is the standard enthalpy of adsorption of the inhibitor.

Rearrangement of equation 7 yields equation 8 and from the logarithm of both side of equation 8, equation 9 were obtained [16]:

$$\frac{CR}{T} = \frac{R}{Nh} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta S_{ads}^0}{T}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta H_{ads}^0}{RT}\right) \quad 8$$

$$\log\left(\frac{CR}{T}\right) = \log\left(\frac{R}{Nh}\right) + \frac{\Delta S_{ads}^0}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta H_{ads}^0}{2.303RT} \quad 9$$

Applying equation 9 to our experimental data from weight loss by plotting values of $\log(CR/T)$ versus $1/T$, a linear relationship with high degree of linearity was obtained as presented in Figure 10. From the slope and intercept of lines on the transition state plot, values of ΔH_{ads} and ΔS_{ads} were calculated and are recorded in Table 4. Mean value of ΔH_{ads} and ΔS_{ads} were found to be -18.527J/mol and 128.694J/mol respectively indicating that the inhibited corrosion reaction of zinc is exothermic and that the inhibition proceeded with increasing entropy.

Figure 10: Transition state plots for the inhibition of the corrosion of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 by TC

Values of free energy of adsorption (ΔG_{ads}) of TC on zinc surface at 303 K were calculated using Gibb Helmolitz equation which is represented by Equation 10 (Ameh, 2014b):

$$\Delta G_{ads} = \Delta H_{ads} - T\Delta S_{ads} \quad 10$$

By substituting values of ΔH_{ads} and ΔS_{ads} , values of ΔG_{ads} were obtained. These values are also recorded in Table 4. Average value of ΔG_{ads} was found to be -39049.14 (39.049kJ/mol). This value is less than the threshold value (-40 kJ/mol) required for the mechanism of chemical adsorption [1]. Generally, values of ΔG_{ads}^0 between 0 and -20 kJ/mol , are consistent with the mechanism of charge transfer from charged inhibitor's molecules to charged metal surface. Therefore the adsorption of TC on the zinc surface is spontaneous and supports the mechanism of physical adsorption.

Table 4: Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of various concentration of TC on zinc surface

System	Slope	Intercept	ΔH_{ads}^0 ($\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol}}$)	ΔS_{ads}^0 ($\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol}}$)	ΔG_{ads}^0 ($\frac{\text{J}}{\text{mol}}$)	R^2
Blank	0.517	-12.495	-9.89907	119.79	-36306.3	0.9335
0.1 g/L	1.052	-10.991	-20.1427	132.22	-40082.8	0.9784
0.2 g/L	1.049	-11.072	-20.08535	131.63	-39903.9	0.9803
0.3 g/L	0.939	-11.496	-17.97917	128.02	-38989.8	0.9851
0.4 g/L	0.913	-11.684	-17.48134	126.54	-38359.1	0.9375
0.5 g/L	0.885	-11.859	-16.94522	125.06	-37910.1	0.9455

3.4. Adsorption study

The adsorption characteristics of TC was studied by fitting data obtained for the degree of surface coverage of the inhibitor into different adsorption isotherms including, Langmuir, Temkin, Flory Huggins, El awardy, Bockris-swinkle, Frumkin and Freundlich adsorption isotherms. The test revealed that the adsorption characteristics of the studied compounds are best described by the Langmuir adsorption isotherm, which can be expressed as follows,

$$\theta = K_{ads}C \times 1/(1+K_{ads}C) \quad 11$$

where C is the concentration of the inhibitor in the bulk electrolyte, θ is the degree of surface coverage of the inhibitor and K_{ads} is the equilibrium constant of adsorption. Transformation of equation 11 yields equation 12,

$$\log(C/\theta) = \log C - \log K_{ads} \quad 12$$

From equation 12, the plots of $\log(C/\theta)$ versus $\log C$ should yield straight lines provided the assumptions establishing the Langmuir adsorption isotherm are valid. Figure 11 show the Langmuir isotherm for the adsorption of TC on zinc surface. The adsorption parameters deduced from the isotherms are presented in Table 5. From the results obtained, it can be seen that the slopes and R^2 values for the Langmuir plots are very close to unity indicating strong adherence of the adsorption data to the Langmuir adsorption model.

Figure 11: Langmuir isotherm for the adsorption of TC on zinc surface in 0.1 M HNO₃ at various temperatures

Table 5: Langmuir parameters for the corrosion of zinc in acid containing various concentrations of the studied inhibitors at various temperatures

T(K)	slope	log K _{ad}	R ²
303	0.808	0.3322	0.9989
313	0.8368	0.2222	0.9945
323	0.8137	0.2361	0.9992
333	0.8270	0.1552	0.997

3.5. Morphological Studies

The surface morphology of the polished zinc coupons in the absence and presence of the inhibitor were studied using scanning electron microscopy. The scanning electron micrographs obtained from the study are presented in Figure 12a, 12b and 12c. The micrograph obtained for the polished zinc metal (Figures 12 a) shows that the metal coupon surface is smooth which is an indication that the zinc used in the study was not corroded prior to immersion in aggressive media. From Figures 12 b, the micro-flakes are clearly visible depicting dissolution of metal surfaces which also indicates that the surface is strongly and uniformly damaged by corrosion due to aggressive media.

However Figure 12c reveals that the surface of the metal in the presence of the inhibitor was smoother than when inhibitor was absent which is an indication that a good protective adsorbed film is formed on the samples [4].

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 12: Scanning electron micrographs of zinc (A) alone (B) in 0.1 M HNO_3 solution (C) in 0.1 M HNO_3 solution plus 0.5 g/L TC

3.6. FTIR study

The FTIR spectrum obtained for TC extract is as presented in Figure 13a while that the FTIR spectrum of the corrosion product of zinc when the extract was used as an inhibitor is given in Figure 13b. Frequencies and peaks of IR adsorption for both cases are presented in Table 6. From the results obtained, it can be seen that the $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bend at 680 cm^{-1} is shifted to 672 cm^{-1} , the $\text{C}-\text{H}$ "oop" at 695 cm^{-1} is shifted to 709 cm^{-1} , the $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ stretch at 1972 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1935 cm^{-1} , the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretch at 1640 cm^{-1} is shifted to 1644 cm^{-1} and the $\text{H}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch at 2858 cm^{-1} was shifted to 2854 cm^{-1} . These shifts indicate that there is interaction between the zinc metal and some molecules in the inhibitor (Ameh et al 2012b, Eddy, 2009). Also the $\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretch $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretch, $\text{O}-\text{H}$ stretch and $\text{C}-\text{H}$ bend and scissoring were missing in the spectrum of the corrosion product indicating that these bond might have been used for bonding between the inhibitor's molecules and the metal.

Figure 13: FTIR spectrum of (A) TC extract (B) the corrosion product of zinc in 0.1 M HNO_3 when TC was used as an inhibitor

Table 6: Frequencies and percentage transmittance of IR absorption by TC extract and the corrosion product when the extract was used as an inhibitor

TC Extract		Corrosion product		Functional Group Assignment
Frequency	% Transmittance	Frequency	% Transmittance	
680	92.841	672	91.399	= C – H bend
695	93.003	709	92.451	C-H ‘oop’
1030	95.813			C – N stretch
1082	96.748			C - O stretch
1156	97.283			C - O stretch
1220	97.342	1220	99.165	- C – H rock
1383	98.851			- C – H bend and scissoring due to alkane
1462	97.161			C - C stretch (in ring)
1640	93.846	1644	95.694	- C = C stretch
1972	99.652	1935	99.677	- C \equiv C stretch
2024	99.400	2009	99.491	- C \equiv C stretch
2095	99.352	2132	99.339	- C \equiv C stretch
2147	99.311	2162	99.345	- C \equiv C stretch
2229	99.477	2229	99.528	- C \equiv N stretch
2858	97.180	2854	100.468	H - C = O stretch
2929	95.261	2921	101.430	H - C = O stretch
3391	85.501			O-H stretch

4. Conclusions

From the results and findings of the study, the following conclusions are made:

- The corrosion of zinc in HNO₃ is a function of temperature, concentration of the acid, concentration of the inhibitor and the period of contact with the aggressive medium.
- *Terminalia catappa* (TC) leaves are a good inhibitor for the corrosion of zinc in HNO₃. The inhibitor is an adsorption inhibitor in that their inhibition efficiencies increased with increase in the concentration of the inhibitor.
- The adsorption of the inhibitor on the surface of zinc metal is spontaneous, exothermic and is consistent with the assumption of Langmuir adsorption isotherm.
- Based on the variation of the inhibition efficiencies of the inhibitor with temperature, values of activation energies and free energies of adsorption, the mechanism of adsorption of the inhibitor points towards physical adsorption.
- Some functional groups of the inhibitor have been used in the formation of bonds and adsorption layer between Zn and the inhibitor which indicates that there is interaction between the inhibitor and the studied metal.

References

- [1]. Ameh, P. O (2018). Electrochemical and computational study of gum *exudates* from *Canarium schweinfurthii* as green corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in HCl solution, *Journal of Taibah University for Science*, 12(6): 783 – 795.
- [2]. Njoku, E.R, (1998). Unpublished Effect of Inhibitors on Corrosion of Mild Steel in HCL Pickling Solution. *M.Sc Thesis Department of Metallurgical Engineering, ABU Zaria-Nigeria.*
- [3]. Loto, R.T., Loto, CA. and Popoola, API. (2012) Effect of Temperature on the Corrosion Inhibition of Trans-4-Hydroxy-4-Stilbazole on Mild Steel in HCl Solution. *International Journal of Corrosion*, 1-7.

- [4]. Ameh, P. O., Magaji, L. & Salihu, T. (2012). Corrosion inhibition and adsorption behaviour for mild steel by *Ficus glumosa* gum in H₂SO₄ solution, *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 6(7): 100 – 106.
- [5]. Ameh, P. O. & Eddy, N. O. (2018a). Theoretical and Experimental Investigations of the Corrosion Inhibition Action of *Piliostigma Thonningii* Extract on Mild Steel in Acidic Medium. *Communication in Physical Sciences*, 3(2): 27-42.
- [6]. Awe F.E., Idris, S.O., Abdulwahab M. & E.E. Oguzie (2015). Theoretical and experimental inhibitive properties of mild steel in HCL by ethanolic extract of *Boscia senegalensis*. *Cogent Chemistry* 1:1 1112676.
- [7]. Eddy, N.O., Ekwumemgbo, P.A. & Mamza, P.A.P. (2009). Ethanol extract of *Terminalia Catappa* as a green inhibitor for the corrosion of mild steel in H₂SO₄. *Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews*, 2: 223-231.
- [8]. De Souza F. A. and Spinelli A. (2008) Caffeic acid as a green corrosion inhibitor for mild steel, *Corrosion Science*, 51(3): 642-649.
- [9]. Abdel-Graber, A.M., Abd-El-Nabey, B.A., Sidahmed, I.M., El-Zayady A.M., & Saadawy, .M. (2006). Inhibitive Action of Some Plant Extracts on the Corrosion of Steel in Acidic Media. *Corrosion Science*, 48 (9);, 2765-2779.
- [10]. Oguzie E.E. (2007) Corrosion inhibition of aluminium in acidic and alkaline media by *Sansevieria trifasciata* extract,” *Corrosion Science* 49: 1527-1539.
- [11]. Rajendran, S., Ganfa Sri V., Arockiaselvi J. & Amalraj A. J. (2005). Corrosion inhibition by plant extracts an overview, *Bulletin of Electrochemistry*, 8: 367-377.
- [12]. Odiongenyi, A. O., Odeomelam, S. A. & Eddy, n. O. (2009). Corrosion and adsorption properties of ethanol extract of *Vernonia Amygdalina* for the corrosion of mild steel in H₂SO₄. *Portugaliae Electrochimica Acta* 27(1): 33-45.
- [13]. Moronkola, D. O. & Ekundayo, O. (2000). Chemical constituents in the fruit essential oil of *Terminalia catappa* Linn (almond fruits). *Journal of Trop. Forest for Research*, 16(1): 72-79.
- [14]. Lasekan, O., Alfi, K., & Abbas, K. A. (2012). Volatile compounds of roasted and steamed Malaysian tropical almond nut (*Terminalia catappa* L.). *International Journal Food Prop.*, 15(5): 1120-1132.
- [15]. Owolabi, M. S., Lawal O. A., Ogunwande, I. A., Hauser R. M., William, N. & Setzer W. N. (2013). Chemical composition of the leaf essential oil of *Terminalia catappa* L. growing in southwestern Nigeria. *American. Journal Essential Oils and Natural Product*, 1(1): 51-54.
- [16]. Ameh, P. O. & Eddy, N. O. (2018b). Experimental and computational chemistry studies on the inhibition efficiency of phthalic acid (PHA) for the corrosion of aluminum in hydrochloric and tetraoxosulphate (VI) acids, *Protection of Metals and Physical Chemistry of Surfaces*, 54(6): 1169–1181.
- [17]. Allam, N. K. (2007). Thermodynamic and quantum chemistry characterization of the adsorption of triazole derivatives during Muntz corrosion in acidic and neutral solutions. *Journal of Applied surface science*, 253: 4570 – 4577.
- [18]. Neelavathi, P., venkatalakshmi, P., & Brindha, P. (2013). Anti bacterial activities of aqueous ethanolic extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaves and back against some pathogenic bacteria. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 5 (1), 114-120.
- [19]. Ameh, P. O. (2014a) Inhibitory action of *Albizia zygia* gum on mild steel corrosion in acid medium *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry* 8(2): 37 - 46.
- [20]. Eddy, N.O. & Ebenso, E. E. (2008). Adsorption and inhibitive properties of ethanol extracts of *Musa sapientum* peels as a green corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in H₂SO₄, *African Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry*, 2(6): 46 – 54.
- [21]. Eddy, N.O, Ameh P. O, & Ali I. (2015). Physicochemical Characterization and Corrosion Inhibition Potential of *Ficus Benjamina* (FB) Gum for Aluminum in 0.1 M HCl. *Walailak Journal of Science and Technology*; 12(12): 1121-1136.

